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The Ethics Of Leadership In Niccolo Machiavelli

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ABSTRACT

The word ethics has its root from the Greek word ‘ethos’ meaning character or way of life. Technically, the term is often used with reference to the study of the principles of human action. Where the study of the principles is normative, ethics is used interchangeably with the study and prescription of rules and regulations regarding the rightness and wrongness of human action. The expression or title ‘The Ethics of Leadership in Nicolo Machiavelli’ is used in reference to those principles, values and norms which, according to Machiavelli underline or justify human actions as they concern leadership. This work, which though largely analytic in method examines the stance of Machiavelli with regard to leadership. The work discovers that Machiavelli departs from the traditional understanding of virtue in favour of a more pragmatic sense that serves for utilitarian purpose. The work is highly descriptive.

Keywords: Ethics, leadership, power and authority

INTRODUCTION

The word ethics has its root from the Greek word ‘ethos’ meaning character or way of life. Technically, the term is often used with reference to the study of the principles of human action. Where the study of the principles is normative, ethics is used interchangeably with the study and prescription of rules and regulations regarding the rightness and wrongness of human action. This approach to ethics determines what is to be done and what is not to be done if the human person is to live a moral life. Where the study of human actions centers on the description of ethical concepts and the description of how human beings behave or act without actually making value judgment or prescribing how human beings should or should not act, the study is known as descriptive ethics. This is the approach that is employed by the social scientists or the behaviorists (Udoidem, 1992).

Of the three approaches, normative ethics is the one that applies to morality properly so called. It deals basically with human beings and how they relate to and treat other beings to promote mutual welfare, growth, creativity, and meaning in striving for what is good over bad and what is right over wrong (Theroux, 1986). Therefore, the expression or title ‘The Ethics of Leadership in Nicolo Machiavelli’ is used in reference to those principles, values and norms which, according to Machiavelli underline or justify human actions as they concern leadership.

POWER AND AUTHORITY: CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION

The use of power and authority by leaders today has come under serious attack, scrutiny and judgment even though both terms can be of great benefits to the roles of governance and leadership. While power is used to enforce the social contract, authority is the mandate a leader has to be in charge. Derived from the French word ‘*pouvoir*’, the word ‘power’ means the ability to perform or carry out a function or task (Ezebuiro, 2021). Russell (1965) and Tawny (1976) conceive power as the production of internal effects

as well as the capacity of an individual, or group of individuals to modify the conduct of other individuals or groups in the manner which he desires. Thomas Hobbes (1651) sees power in terms of everyone agreeing to forgo his or her rights and conferring same upon one or an assemblage of persons that might reduce all their Wills by plurality of voices, unto one Will. So, power in this sense is the abolition of rights of other people. Hume (1749) understands power in the same as authority. For him, power is depended on obedience; hence there would be no power worth fearing unless there were motives of obedience other than the fear of power.

Authority is the competence to make judgement which reasonable persons or lesser competence will accept as certainly or probably true. It is also a special capacity to give direction which generate a non-absolute moral duty to obey. A leader is one who has both power and authority. However, one may have power without a corresponding authority. But anyone with authority also has power attached to it.

Nigeria as a country has witnessed frequent abuse of power and authority, lack of sovereignty of the people, power tussle and the quest to remain in power against all odds without considering the interest of the people. In Nigeria, the cry of marginalization echoes everywhere; between the Igbos and Yorubas, North and South); hence the clamor for restructuring continues to sound. All these have become necessary as redefining the concept of power and authority for leaders and would-be leaders becomes an imperative.

Niccolo Machiavelli (1469-1527) seriously doubted the feasibility of ideal states offered by those philosophers who came before him. He believed that without developing a reliable ethical foundation of leadership, the end is unattainable and this can lead to a useless venture. For him, strong ethical foundation of leadership is necessary as it is also important if a leader or would-be leader is to lead well. No doubt, Machiavelli advocated for a pragmatic ethical leadership anchored on some pragmatic ethical principles.

This paper therefore examines this form of ethical leadership as advocated and canvassed by Machiavelli. The work inquires on the subject of leadership—man. What does it mean to be a human being in the view of Machiavelli? What are the qualities of a good leader? Who should lead? Are there grounds to justify a good leadership? All these questions and worries will be laid to rest as we progress step by step in this paper.

BACKGROUND TO MACHIAVELLI'S ETHICS OF LEADERSHIP

Machiavelli's ethics of leadership can be said to be based on two distinctive factors. The first is his experience of how to achieve an end result in any enterprise embarked upon by human beings. On this, Machiavelli was so much concerned with how (means) and end (result) of actions. He thinks that without proper methodology, and strategic planning, it is futile embarking on any mission by methods that are bound to fail. Therefore, in his work, *The Prince and The Discourses*, one reads Machiavelli trying to draw conclusion from factual observations of how people actually base their activities on empirical methods.

One must recall that prior to the emergence of *The Prince*, it was customary to believe that there is a special relationship between moral goodness and legitimate authority. But with Machiavelli on the scene, this moralistic view of authority was criticized. Consequently, Machiavelli tried to exclude issues of authority and legitimacy from morality (Machiavelli, 1976). His view was that the traditional sense of morality does not and cannot guarantee good leadership. Thus, while *The Prince* is no doubt, the most widely read of all his works, *The Discourse on the Ten Books of Titus Livy* perhaps is the one that expresses Machiavelli's personal beliefs and commitments about leadership, politics and mortality.

Obviously, Machiavelli provides a psychological case that the realities of human character tend to favor republicanism over a principality since, for him, the former "is better able to adapt itself to diverse circumstances that a prince owing to the diversity found among its citizens" (Machiavelli, 1976: 14,285-287). With this therefore, Machiavelli, in *The Discourses on Livy* developed a comprehensive theory about liberty and government and of course leadership or how to lead which arises from his observation from the experiences and constant study of human affairs. The work further deals with "military prowess, formations, strategies, results and failures given certain methods" (Machiavelli, 1976: 14). He thinks the

power of a supreme is basically “to control and make every other aspect to conform with his consideration” (Nwoko, 1988: 59).

On the second factor or motivation, it is believed that Machiavelli’s traditionalist worldview originated from his adoption of the Renaissance cosmology, physics, and astrological natural philosophy. All of these tend to postulate unity of nature, the skies, things of the world, and human beings (Parel, 1992). Machiavelli believes that for human beings to succeed in any enterprise or any of their creative endeavors, their conduct must be in line with the quality of the time (what he terms the given conditions). Thus, even with all the limitations imposed by the sky, fate, and quality of time, Machiavelli’s cosmology does leave room for human autonomy, the *vita activa* and virtue—which he defines as an individual’s sense of activism, public-spiritedness and dedication to the common good rather than just their own interest (Machiavelli, 1976).

MACHIAVELLI’S POINT OF DEPARTURE

Some basic elements derivable from Machiavelli’s ethics of leadership are relevant to mention here. According to Nwoko (2006), Machiavelli deviates from the medieval teachings on the end of man by contending that the end of man is solely earthly and not heavenly. It is in the achievement of power, greatness and fame and immortalizing fame. For him, man has no supernatural end. There is therefore no divine law; hence virtue is the ability to attain power and fame. Man does not attain goodness only by being subject to law.

Machiavelli teaches that man’s life or history is determined by fear and virtue. Man can mould his fate by working and intervening in the course of life and history. And fortune comes through this intervention. The ability of man to make this intervention and achieve the greatness of power and fame is virtue.

Machiavelli does not see the need for the Aristotelian type of the division of government into three good forms and three bad forms. A good form of government for him should constitute a mixture of aristocracy, monarchy and democracy. This mixture supported by adequate representation will give various classes in the society the opportunity to influence the power of each other and thereby assure a wider scope of freedom for all.

For Machiavelli, political dissention and opposition are necessary elements to preserve liberty in the state (Scruton, 1982). But the rule of law supersedes factions and depravity and vengeance. Thus, a constitution should defend against usurpation of power. Power should rather be distributed, giving good opportunity to impeach any person in the service of the state, no matter the position, when necessary.

Between *Republics* and *Principlities*, Machiavelli believes that all forms of the state and powers under which men have been governed are either *Republic* or *Principlities* (Machiavelli, 1981).

THE SUBJECT OF LEADERSHIP

Machiavelli did not waste time talking about leadership without his teaching and understanding of who the subject of leadership is. He thinks a comprehensive knowledge of the human nature paves way for a thorough knowledge of who is to lead. Machiavelli bluntly believes that the human nature is the most bestial of animal species. This is because, as a general rule, he holds that humans are unreliable and selfish by nature (Stumph, 2003). Under this belief, he assumed that under some conditions, the human persons can be led to believe in ways that are good or led to be good. He also believes that the human nature can be overcome, and manipulated through braveness, courage and virtue even though it does not arrive at any excellence because good always goes alongside evil (Machiavelli, 1976).

Machiavelli further assumes that people are guided to be good through an art which can create good laws and good armies by effective leaders. He also thinks that human nature is malleable to the degree that the natural selfishness and shortsightedness of most people can be overcome. On this account, one can say that for Machiavelli, the human nature is intrinsically evil. And man cannot be trusted because of his egoistic acquisitive tendencies. More so, one can say that for Machiavelli, with the conditioning of man, he can overcome his evil nature and become good. The last important point here is that for Machiavelli, efficient leadership needs both skill (virtue) and fortune. A leader, he says, needs practical virtue which is

not necessarily moral virtue to be able to hold the people under his check and elicit good conduct from them (Machiavelli, 1976: 65, 279-282).

HUMAN NATURE AND POLITICAL LEADERSHIP

Machiavelli's view or understanding of the human nature informs his theory about leadership and authority. He believes that what works is governed by human nature, the way people are, and people are not wholly good. Machiavelli's view of the human nature entails that people are volatile and need coordination if order is to be achieved. Consequently, he conceives fear as a key policy to subdue these aspects of the human nature. On this basis, Machiavelli advocates that for good laws to exist, there must be armies to coerce people to submission. Good armies, he says, "will make people to fear being punished...(In other words), it will coerce the masses into abiding the law (Machiavelli, 1976: 65).

Machiavelli understand the purpose of leadership as to protect life and maintain law and order. It is on this belief that he advocates that a leader must be able to preserve life. A leader must be able "to check the excesses of people; their selfish ends imbued in their nature and build a strong society that protects the possessions of its people" (Machiavelli, 1976: 279).

LEADERSHIP IN MACHIAVELLI

In his writing, Machiavelli demonstrates who a leader is or ought to be. He does this by examining two kinds of government, namely monarchy and republic. In both systems, Machiavelli claims a leader merges out of necessity or need; hence his argument that 'fortune' makes rulers and also ends rulership. In republican government, for example, Machiavelli argues that leadership arises "when one with virtue and fortune chooses to liberate his people and shows his prowess by drawing people to his side and gaining their support (Machiavelli, 1976: 36). Consequently, such a person gets the peoples' authority to rule over them. In Monarchy on the other hand, Machiavelli argues that one with fortune and virtue rises to form a great army; showing the ability to do great deeds. For him, in doing this, the people will come with both fear and love over such a leader who by this time, has surrounded himself with good friends and ministers (Machiavelli, 1976: 65, 279-282).

One of the ways, according to Machiavelli, a ruler could prove his ability to lead/rule is how he handles "external affairs and never yielding to neutrality." A leader always "takes a definite stand while preparing for whatever outcomes it generates." A ruler also encourages "his subjects to engage in fruitful ventures like agriculture" (Machiavelli, 1976: 331-335,369).

MACHIAVELLI'S AGENDA: DEMONSTRATION OF LEADERSHIP VIRTU IN PRINCIPALITY AND REPUBLIC

To understand Machiavelli's agenda in the context of ethics of leadership, it is important to examine his description of the two systems of government that he advocates. And note how he describes and underlines virtue as common good in the republic. In doing so, we shall adopt Njoku's presentation since his correctly gives us the basic element in Machiavelli's description that we seek to have.

According to Nwoko (2006: 60-62), on republics, Machiavelli makes it clear in the Discourse on the First Decade of Titus Livinus that republics are free states as different from principalities, which are not free states. The republics rank higher in their organization and structuring than the principalities. They bear high advantage also. Only a people with higher degree of virtue can form a true republic. This is because it implies a constitution, a self-government (not merely representative democracy) unlike a principality where a prince or tyrant must subjugate the people because they lack virtue and cannot govern themselves.

So, for Machiavelli, in the republic, the people have the freedom to rule. In fact, it is the people that should rule. Power, he admits, belongs to the people. Machiavelli gives a reason for this position. According to him, the common people (the public) are to be given sovereign authority if one wishes to create and maintain a genuine civic and free way of life (Machiavelli, 1976: 168). The people, he says, are more prudent and stable than the princes. The people can judge better; external forces of corrupt judgment

influence them less than the princes. In their election, they make better choices than princes who would be easily lured to choose dubious characters. Even on the question of law, although the price could make better laws, institutions, statutes etc. but the people would keep them better. Thus, “the virtue of a good people is always higher than that of the prince. They are free” (Machiavelli, 1982:58).

It is freedom, according to Machiavelli that a state a republic. It is the virtue of the people that make them free. Freedom of the state, therefore, means not only independence from external determination, it involves also the internal freedom of the people. The ancient republic was earlier a free state but later became unfree when the emperors and Caesars started to concentrate political powers in their hands and discarded the peoples’ constitution.

On the other hand, the freedom of the state is not a mere liberality. It is rather in the people’s self-government. Self-government is not simply representative democracy but the people accepting with virtue the challenges of guiding their lives according to legal and institutional structure of the state. They would freely and spontaneously, without compulsion, keep order. Actually,

It is virtue that makes a people a free state. It is this power (virtu) that is the ability with which man can challenge fortune which confronts his effort towards order and life. Virtu, therefore is displayed in the power or ability to resist the natural force that tend to lure men to believe “that human affairs are so governed by fortune and by God, that men cannot alter them by any prudence of theirs, and indeed have no remedy against them (Machiavelli, 1981 :100-101).

It is, therefore, this ability or power of a people to control the force that governs the universe (which is believed to be fortune) that makes them conform to laws and institutions; it builds up for them a constitutional systema republic. This ability once achieved in a people as a free state, aims at two ends, namely; to expand their state always and to protect their liberties (Machiavelli, 1981:58).

VIRTUE AS COMMON GOOD IN THE REPUBLIC: A LEADER’S PREOCCUPATION

As a way of demonstrating the virtue a leader should possess, Machiavelli takes time to study the common good in the republic. For Machiavelli, what will preoccupy the mind of a good leader is how to protect the common good. But unlike the Aristotelian-Thomistic understanding of the common good, Machiavelli believes that a good leader recognizes the common good as the special virtue in the republic. For him, the common good is only respected in the republics not in the principalities because the prince is prone to protect the private interest of the few when it conflicts with that of the generality of the people. And this always makes the principalities less prosperous in wealth and in power. However, in Machiavelli’s own words, we read: “it is not individual property, but the general good that makes cities great; and certainly, the general good is regarded nowhere but in the Republic... (Machiavelli, 1981:102).

THE SOVEREIGN OR PRINCE AND HIS POWER

Beyond the demonstration of common good as the virtue in the republic, Machiavelli goes further to describe principalities from two angles, namely principalities that are ‘hereditary’ and ‘new’ (new in the sense that it is formed either entirely new or members are annexed to the hereditary state of the prince. Accordingly, Machiavelli holds that although in human history men acknowledge and praise honest princes who keep their power by law, the successful princes are the crafty ones who adopt force (there are two ways of contesting for power: by law, which is appropriate to men, and by force, which belongs to the beast). Here, Machiavelli ironically describes the true virtue of a leader. For example, he says that for a prince to be successful, he has to adopt the way of the fox to know the snares and the lion to frighten the wolves. In this way, he claims the prince can keep his power, although that would be wrong if men were entirely good. Machiavelli’s sense of virtue is ironically opposite to the traditional sense and understanding of virtue as highlighted above. He admits that in order to keep faith in his

power, the sovereign can also deceive men. Machiavelli cites that the success of Alexander VI was because he was the greatest deceiver ever. He declares:

A prince therefore needs not necessarily have all the good qualities...but he should certainly appear to have them...if he has these qualities and always behaves to have them, he will find them harmful, if he only appears to have them, they will render him service. He should appear to be compassionate, faithful to his word, kind, guiltless, and devout. And indeed, he should be so. But his dispositions should be such that, if he needs to be the opposite, he knows how (Machiavelli, 1981: 100-101).

It is the conviction of Machiavelli that they should avoid being despised (Machiavelli, 1982: 102). According to him in order to win the favour of the people, the prince must avoid those things that would make people hate him or treat him with contempt, such as being greedy or grasping, violating other people's rights. This will endear him to many people. He would have only the task to fight ambitious people. He must also avoid appearing fickle, frivolous, cowardly irresolute, or effeminate, since these would make him contemptible. He should show courage, greatness and fortitude.

When settling disputes between his subjects, he should ensure that his judgment is irrevocable; and he should be so regarded that no one ever dreams of trying to deceive or trick him (Machiavelli 1982:102).

According to him, this assures him of his place and power. His external security is consolidated by arming himself well and by good allies, while internal security is assured by his observance of the aforementioned attitudes, which will frighten his enemies.

CONCLUSION

This work sets out to present Machiavelli's ethics of leadership. The essence of this presentation is to see how Machiavelli understands virtue and leadership. It is obvious that Machiavelli's understanding and preoccupation with virtue and leadership differs strongly from the traditional Aristotelian-Thomistic perspective upon which the idea of the common good is at the center of virtue and leadership. Ironically, Machiavelli's presentation of virtue as an ability of a leader to be crafty, and subdues his subjects using any means possible indicates that ethics of leadership in the philosophy of Machiavelli is prone to multiple interpretations. One would rather admit that Machiavelli was a pragmatic thinker in his submissions. This is true notwithstanding that the problem with the several interpretations that Machiavelli's principle has been subjected to is due to its constant omission of his passionate side while bringing forward the brute side of his leadership scheme as well as failure to marry his two books together. It is also a failure to see the practical expediency of *The Prince* to address the socio-political evils and instability of any nation with the aim of training to the political ideas of the Discourse.

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